

Resilient Communications for the First Responders at the field

Athanasios Douklias
ICCS
Athens, Greece
thanasis.douklias@iccs.gr

Maria Krommyda
ICCS
Athens, Greece
maria.krommyda@iccs.gr

Angelos Amditis
ICCS
Athens, Greece
a.amditis@iccs.gr

Abstract—Rescue operations in both small-scale emergencies and major natural or man-made disasters are very challenging. The first responders are requested to explore unknown and potentially hazardous environments, risking their own well-being in order to save others. New innovative technologies are essential to support the first responders in their tasks, ensuring their safety and the effectiveness of their operations. These technologies, that may include wearable devices, automated vehicles and drones or back-end services require communications in order to operate in full capacity. Available infrastructure often fail in cases of emergency, while some operational environments may not even support them to begin with. Aiming to alleviate this barrier, a resilient, field deployable system, that can support the communication between all the equipment deployed at the field and multiple backhaul networks is presented here. The design of the communications, the hardware solutions that support the design as well as the selected configurations are discussed in detail.

Index Terms—field communications, resilience, first responders, emergency response, field operations, operational environment, backhaul networks, system design

I. INTRODUCTION

Rescue operations range from small scale emergencies, that are more often than not limited within one small geographic area and handled by one discipline of responders, to major disasters, either natural or man-made, that may be spread across many different incident areas and involve complex response operations and cross-agency collaboration. In all cases, the first responders are asked to take many risks and operate under unknown, possible hazardous or life-threatening, situations where time is of the essence [1].

To this end, many technologies have been developed aiming to support the first responders during the field operations, increase their situational awareness and their timely notification in case of changes to the operational plan [2]. A system, to provide all these needs, is being developed within the context of the INGENIOUS project [3], that aims to assist first responders when operating at the field, increasing their efficiency and their situational awareness and decreasing their response time. To achieve that the development of a Next Generation Integrated Toolkit (NGIT) for Collaborative Response is undertaken to increase the protection level of the first responders and augment their operational capacity when responding to incidents.

The first responder (FR) is given a series of wearable devices, either integrated in the equipment already used by them, such as the helmet, the uniform and the boots or independent such as a vital signs sensor bracelet. Next the FRs have access to multiple unmanned aerial vehicles, that can be used based on the needs of the response plan and some back-end services that consolidate the received information, provide it to the Command and Control center and communicate alerts and changes regarding the response plan to the FRs.

The devices and services provided aim to collect information from the field timely and efficiently, support the evaluation of the incident, provide important information to all FRs and cross-agency team leaders as needed, and support the collaboration of different agencies and the analysis of the possible solutions and changes needed to the response plan. As it is obvious from the functionalities discussed, key role to the smooth deployment of the NGIT have the stable communications between FRs at the field and Command and Control centers.

Such communications may seem trivial when discussed out of context, but it is known that during emergencies, especially large scale disasters, communication infrastructure can suffer as well and in many cases backhaul networks are unavailable [4], [5]. Combining that with the topological challenges and the need for minimal response and deployment time the field communications during response operations are a very challenging problem [6].

Contributions. A resilient, field deployable communication system, that can support the data exchanges between all the equipment deployed at the field, utilize multiple backhaul networks based on their availability and ensure that the Command and Control center has the latest overview of the operational picture is presented here. The system has been designed to:

- Provide resilient communications in any environment and field conditions;
- Support the exchange of information between FRs, including urban and rural environments, indoor to outdoors and outdoors to indoors communications;
- Stream to the back-end services all the collected information even when there are high throughput demands;
- Provide a network management system, allowing the field coordinator to monitor the connected devices and producing alerts in case of disconnections;

- Be safe for the responders to use, utilizing state-of-the-art equipment designed for outdoor conditions, along with proper ruggedization and safety measures that have been included in the system design;
- Be easily deployable, requiring from the responder to only power on the system, with all the services starting automatically after that.

The proposed system will be demonstrated this year at 18 small scale field training exercises that will be organised by one or two emergency response disciplines and at two large scale field training exercises where multiple disciplines will participate, aiming to improve the cross-agency collaboration and the establishment of common response plans.

II. USER REQUIREMENTS & SYSTEM DESIGN

Based on recent studies and semi-structured interviews with FRs [7], it is clear that there is no easy “one size fits all” communications technology solution for all disciplines. There are, however, some core traits that systems must provide in order to be trusted and tested at the field. The FRs want to utilize communication solutions that are dependable, easy to use, cover the communication needs at the field, and are based on user-centered design principles [8].

Within the context of this project, the user requirements were collected over multiple interaction with the responders. Initially, dedicated end-user workshops for all the components of the NGIT were conducted, to familiarize the users with their potential functionalities and objectives. Based on the received feedback, for each component an initial list of functionalities and system requirements was composed. Then a dedicated focus group per component was held where these were presented to the FRs for evaluation.

Specifically for the field deployable communications, given their holistic nature, a second focus group was conducted after all others, where the initial system design was presented and the way the user requirements and the challenged are tackled was discussed in length with the FRs to ensure their agreement.

In a nutshell, the user requirements for the field deployable communications, which lead to specific design decisions as it are presented in the next paragraphs, are the following:

- **Resilient network.** The FRs operate in unknown working environment under unpredictable situations. More often than not, in cases of major disasters, commonly used communication infrastructure is not available or reliable. Also, the number of FRs and agencies that respond to an incident are dynamic, changing constantly along with the current picture at the field, so the devices to be connected to the network are unknown. Based on these, the FRs require a resilient network that offers multiple solutions in cases common communication infrastructures are unavailable and scales dynamically as needed.
- **Large volumes of data.** Most toolkits aim to offer to the FRs a wide range of functionalities that can support them in diverse scenarios. To this end, there are high

Fig. 1: INGENIOUS network overview

throughput demands, along with video streaming from multiple sources combined with near real-time needs. On top of that there is also the need for minimal information loss and message prioritization.

- **Multiple topologies.** Similarly with the working environment that is unknown before response operations, there are multiple topologies that the field deployable communications should support. These include wide area communication, connectivity between multiple locations, indoors to outdoors and outdoors to indoors connectivity and support for both urban and rural environment.
- **Safety & deployment.** Any equipment used at the field during operations should be safe for the FRs. This includes proper ruggedization, safety measure about extreme environmental conditions, battery management following all the specifications as well as all the measures for carrying this equipment comfortably, for example without overheating. At the same time, the equipment should be easy to deploy, requiring no technical knowledge from the FR and no at the field configuration that may be time consuming and error prone.
- **Network management.** Operational commanders want to know the number and type of devices that are connected at the field, the volume and rate of the produced information as well as the last message received from each one. In order to support that, a network management system should be provided, to keep a real-time inventory of the devices connected to it and produce alerts for specific events, such as disconnections or unresponsiveness.

The field deployable communications include the field equipment and the network management system. The field deployable equipment provides proprietary communication infrastructure and access to a resilient network, that supports the needs of the NGIT at the field. There are some important technical challenges regarding the design of the field deployable communications given the user requirements discussed above.

In order to offer an infrastructure that meets all these requirements, multiple technologies are employed, each target-

ing a specific type of network size, along with a communication gateway that integrates multiple network interfaces into a single routing node. The two networks of different sizes along with the WAN interfaces that are necessary for the identified needs, as shown in Figure 1, are presented here.

a) *Personal Area Network (PAN)*: The PAN is based on Bluetooth connectivity which has as a main requirement the presence of a master node. Based on the NGIT architecture the master node is the Smart Uniform and the network includes all the message exchanges from the equipment worn by the FRs as part of their personal gear. The PAN offers a maximum data rate between 1 and 4 Mbps and range up to 10 meters, fully supporting the communication needs of the wearable gear.

b) *Local Area Network (LAN)*: During the design and the deployment of the LAN sufficient coverage and bandwidth provision should be ensured to support the communication needs of the NGIT, which include the continuous streaming of visual and thermal video from multiple sources, the uploading of large files from the automated vehicles and drones as well as the indoor to outdoor communication between FRs. In order to achieve that, modular and flexible equipment has been selected, that can be deployed following different spatial placements ensuring that all the requirements are met. The main technology utilized by the LAN is 802.11ax, as it is presented in detail in the following section.

c) *Wide Area Network (WAN) interfaces*: Those interfaces ensure that the information collected at the field can reach the Command and Control center of the FRs regardless of its location, e.g. deployed centrally at a different location. This communication is achieved through the base station. The base station, in addition to offering the LAN for the communications at the fields, provides also multiple backhaul networks [9]. In both the technical and commercial definitions, backhaul generally refers to the side of the network that communicates with the global Internet, paid for at wholesale commercial access rates to or at an Internet exchange point or other core network access location.

In the designed system, the backhaul technology is dynamically decided based on the available infrastructure at the time of the incident. The technologies used by the system are:

- Satellite communication;
- DSL variants, such as ADSL, VDSL;
- Point-to-point microwave radio relay transmission;
- 4G broadband cellular network technology.

The deployment of the communications at the field is kept as simplified as possible. The FRs are asked to select an easily accessible point within the mission field where they can set up the base station, the antenna mast with the pre-mounted access point and the power module. As soon as the base station is powered on, all the services are deployed and the LAN is accessible. In case the mission field is too large or too complex topologically to be covered by only one access point, then additional access points can be deployed just as easy as the first one in other locations.

Fig. 2: Major components of the INGENIOUS communications toolkit.

III. FIELD DEPLOYABLE EQUIPMENT

Based on the above analysis, for the local area network, the necessary hardware equipment has been selected with the major components depicted in figure 2 and described in more detail in the following.

a) *Mobile broadband modem*: Although at times of disaster broadband cellular networking cannot be relayed on due to cell overloading or damage to the internet service provider's equipment, because it's a cheap and highly available solution for internet connectivity any communication solution should be able to take advantage of an available cellular network. To this end, in the field deployable equipment, the 4G router of choice is the Teltonika RUT950 [10]. It is a high-performance industrial 4G LTE WiFi router designed as a Main/Backup internet source that can hold two SIM cards and is able to auto switch between them in cases of weak signal, data connection fail or data limit. It is complimented by an external 3G/4G LTE 2X2 Multiple Input, Multiple Output (MIMO) omnidirectional antenna with a gain of 12 dBi. This is to take advantage of the known orientation of the antenna and the relaxed space

restrictions to achieve better signal to noise ratio than cell phones and thus higher data transmission rates.

b) *Satellite communication terminal*: Satellite communication is one of the most expensive communication methods and has a limited bandwidth. However, it has the highest availability and is the most resilient making it a must have for a communications toolkit targeting FRs. The Cobham Explorer 540 satellite terminal [11] is included here. It is a 20cm x 20cm lightweight rugged IP66 design, offers up to 464 kbps of data rate and can be installed in a timely manner due to its audio assisted satellite pointing functionality.

c) *Point to Point link*: Point to Point microwave links make possible the bridging of fixed locations separated by large distances while offering high bandwidths. They are included here to provide an additional WAN interface in case there is internet connectivity available at some remote but reachable location, there is a need for connectivity at a secondary location not within the initial LAN or to connect additional access points to the base station.

The long range and high bandwidth communication capability is due to the directive antennas used at both ends. The higher the antenna gains the longer the distance that can be bridged for a given transmission speed but at the same time the more narrow the beamwidth is. The later leads to time consuming and not always successful alignment procedures and as a result a suitable choice must be made between antenna gain and ease of installation. The HG3-TP-S30 [12] antenna with a 3dB beamwidth of 21 degrees and gain of 18.4 dBi, has been chosen, which combined with the ePMP 1000 connectorized radio [13] form the complete solution.

d) *Power Supply Module*: The field communications need to be powered autonomously for as long as the mission at the field lasts. In contrast with other components of the NGIT that have as a time restriction the field operating hours of the FRs and can rely on battery exchanges during short breaks, the field communications should be able to operate continuously for extended time periods. In order to achieve the greatest versatility for the designed system in regard to power supply it is designed to be compatible with a 230V/50Hz power supply. This means that it can be powered with a series of ways, including directly from a main power supply if available, using a gasoline powered generator or a portable battery power station.

In full deployment, for missions without a specific time duration, a hybrid solution that includes both a gasoline and a battery powered generator is proposed. The idea is that the system can be supplied by the portable battery power station which in turn is charged by the gasoline power generator. This setup allows for power generator refuelling and accounts for a potential breakdown of the generator. Additionally, unattended operation for several hours is possible if needed. The infrastructure has been carefully selected to ensure that the gasoline powered generator is powerful enough to charge the battery power station sufficiently and ensure that there won't be any interruptions to the provided services.

The gasoline powered generator included in the deployable equipment is the Honda EU10i Generator [14], which can deliver 1000W. It weighs 13 Kg, it includes a highly efficient Honda 4-stroke engine and a 2.3 litre fuel tank. The generator is based on Inverter technology which combined with the sound proofed casing keeps operational noise to just $52dB(a)$ at 7m. It achieves up to eight hours running time on a single tank at $\frac{1}{4}$ load and offers 12V 8A DC output for recharging batteries.

The portable battery power station included in the deployable equipment is the PowerOak PS7 [15], a compact solution for portable power, with 6.4Wh/100g energy capacity, which allows it to offer 1000Wh with 15.6Kg weight. It is rated at 600W and provides 12V DC output, USB-C and USB-A output as well as two 230V AC outputs, covering not only the needs of the field communications but also allowing the FRs to charge other devices or equipment if needed.

e) *Base station*: The base station is the component responsible for establishing the wireless LAN. It provides for the main connectivity of the majority of the equipment included in the NGIT and is comprised by two key sub-components, an access point and an antenna mast.

Antenna mast. One of the most important parameters in field deployments of communication infrastructure is the antenna height as it is a major factor when it comes to determining the covered area and the minimization of interference. According to the recommendation ITU-R P.1411 [16] the antenna height above ground provides for the determination of a break point, above which the path loss increases rapidly. In addition whether the antenna clears most of the surrounding obstacles determines the particular path loss model to be applied with the models applicable to antenna heights greater than the surrounding obstacles being more forgiving in terms of attenuation.

It is thus important to provide with the means to adjust the antenna height. In order to achieve that, a foldable antenna mast is deployed, that provides with the ability to adjust the antenna height, giving the opportunity to dynamically select the right height based on the specific topological situation at the deployment area. The main requirements are that it should be able to carry a weight of up to 6 kg at the top, extend to a height of up to 8 meters, be compound and easily deployed.

Furthermore, it should provide with the means to mount the rest of the equipment, 4G antenna, Satellite terminal, router, etc. on its base. For the system designed here, it has been decided to have a custom made antenna mast in order to achieve the lowest possible weight that only a solution tailored to the given specifications can provide.

Access Point. The LAN network is set up by an 802.11ax [17] Access Point (AP). The 802.11ax standard, also known as WiFi 6, offers several key improvements over the previous generations of WiFi networks that are applicable to the INGENIOUS use case, namely:

- A more efficient medium access control method, *orthogonal frequency division multiple access*, that in contrast to

the *carrier-sense multiple access with collision avoidance* is able to mitigate collisions by allocating parts of the spectrum to the various station devices and so move the network from a contention to schedule based service. This is important for this use case, since the LAN network must support multiple devices, with different bandwidth needs, transmitting data simultaneously to the AP and thus competing for air time.

- Longer Symbol duration and guard interval. In outdoor deployments a primary concern is inter symbol interference. 802.11ax uses a 4 times longer symbol duration and up to 4 times longer guard interval, at 3.2 us. This makes possible larger cell sizes and due to both increasing the symbol duration and the guard interval the data rate remains unchanged and is even improved for shorter guard intervals [18].
- 802.11ac allowed for multi-user MIMO transmissions only from the AP to the stations. This was advantageous in usage scenarios when the stations mostly download data but in INGENIOUS the situation is the opposite, due to the need to upload video streams and sensor data to support the creation of a common operational picture. With WiFi 6 the same is possible for uplink transmissions as well, enhancing the networks throughput [19].

While 802.11ax standard offers several advantages on each own, the AP itself can add to those for a better overall result. APs can offer multiple radios able to operate at different frequencies which helps to partition the clients into multiple physical networks and at the same time exploit the different propagation characteristics of 2.4 and 5 GHz bands.

The AirEngine 8760R – X1E [20], a next generation, high-performance outdoor AP that fully comply with WiFi 6, 802.11ax, standard is included in the deployable equipment. It is available with 8 external omnidirectional antennas to support 8x8 multi-user MIMO, features a dual radio and is IP68 certified for outdoor deployments. Equally important is its extensive management information base that provides information per station device and enables the configuration of wireless multimedia extension parameters of the stations to provide programmable Quality of Service over the wireless network.

f) *Open source software router*: The open source software router is required to be both powerful enough to route the large volumes of network traffic produced by the LAN and run open source software. In addition it must have no less than five Ethernet ports to be able to host the multiple WAN interfaces and connect to the access point of the LAN. To meet those specifications the Protecli Vault 6 Port [21] is used. It features an Intel i5 CPU, up to 64 GB of RAM, six Ethernet ports and can host the Linux operating system. On top of it run the software packages that perform the routing and the network management.

IV. NETWORK ARCHITECTURE & MANAGEMENT

The field deployable equipment forms a network that is complemented by an abstraction layer, implemented by the

Fig. 3: Network architecture

OpenDaylight Controller [22], that offers a RESTful API. Through this API, it is possible to configure the network and retrieve information regarding its operation. As presented in figure 3, through southbound OpenFlow and Simple Network Management Protocol (SNMP) plugins the OpenDaylight Controller is able to interact with the AP’s SNMP agent and the OpenvSwitch powered device connecting the LAN with the multiple WAN interfaces and perform the intended network function virtualization.

The RESTCONF API of the northbound interface is employed by the application to provide network configuration and monitoring in order to adjust to network changes and support the field coordinator in knowing the number and type of devices that are operable in the field at any given moment, notify as needed for events related with disconnections of devices or unresponsiveness.

Network Topology. One of the most important things when deploying equipment at the field is to know which of the devices are connected and transmitting data properly and which have been disconnected. This information is available for the field commander and also forwarded to the Command and Control center. A device disconnection could mean that the FR carrying it is now operating outside the range of the LAN or that there is some hardware malfunction. Regardless the reason, the appropriate personnel must be informed in case of loss of communication with a device, to ensure the safety of the FR and to alert the rest of the team for this issue.

For a network this means that the network topology must be monitored and events generated when a change arises. To this end, messages in case of disconnection or reconnection of a device and the change in the availability of the WAN interfaces are sent along with a periodic list of all the devices participating in the network. For the WiFi stations the received signal strength indicator of each device is reported as well, to provide an early warning of a possible loss of communication.

In addition statistics about the network’s operation are collected to analyze the performance of the proposed solution and, if needed, to be used for the selection of proper correction actions to be implemented in the next field trials.

Quality of service. The NGIT offers a wide range of functionalities provided by a plethora of components. While all the provided information is important for increasing the

situational awareness and fine-tuning the operation response plan, there is clear prioritization regarding data exchanges that are crucial for the safety and well being of the FRs. Such messages include alerts for hardware malfunctions, voice communications and commands send from the Command and Control center to the field personnel.

This adheres to an important network requirement, that of quality of service. In this case different priorities to different services and users across the established network must be provided. This is achieved through the OpenDaylight Controller which manipulates the setting of the WiFi stations, access point and switch to provide a uniform prioritization. Furthermore, there is a need for this prioritization to be dynamic due to the requirement for resilience. In case one of the WAN interfaces becomes unavailable the system has to adjust to a possible restriction in the backhaul bandwidth along with increased operation cost.

For this reason key services, such as voice communication, and important users, such as team commanders, are given priority based on the current status of the network with the rest of the traffic even dropped completely. Finally, there is the possibility for the application to receive messages dictating the services and users to receive priority in order to implement an event based prioritization. The idea here is that during emergencies personnel involved in an specific incident maybe need to be given priority over other assets deployed in the field.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the complete system design for deploying a resilient communications network at the field during emergency responses has been presented. The system offers two networks with different sizes, one for the personal equipment of the FR and one for the operational area, coupled with the needed WAN interfaces and a dynamic backhaul network connectivity for the connection with the Command and Control center and the back-end services.

It has been carefully designed in order to meet all the identified requirements of the FRs when operating at the field. To this end, the system can provided high throughput as needed for all the equipment and services, can be reliably deployed even in unknown topologies while at the same time ensures the safety of the FRs and provides full monitoring of the provided services.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work is part of the INGENIOUS project. INGENIOUS has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 Research & Innovation Programme under GA no. 833435 and the Korean Government. Content reflects only the authors' view.

REFERENCES

- [1] A. Mason, S. Drew, and D. Weaver, "Managing crisis-induced uncertainty: First responder experiences from the 2011 joplin-duquesne tornado," *International JDRR*, vol. 23, pp. 231 – 237, 2017.
- [2] G. Baldini, S. Karanasios, D. Allen, and F. Vergari, "Survey of wireless communication technologies for public safety," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 16, no. 2, pp. 619–641, 2014.
- [3] INGENIOUS. (2020) The first responder (fir) of the future: a next generation integrated toolkit (ngit) for collaborative response, increasing protection and augmenting operational capacity. <https://ingenious-first-responders.eu/>.
- [4] M. L. Vanderford, T. Nastoff, J. L. Telfer, and S. E. Bonzo, "Emergency communication challenges in response to hurricane katrina: Lessons from the centers for disease control and prevention," *Journal of Applied Communication Research*, vol. 35, no. 1, pp. 9–25, 2007.
- [5] C. T. BUTTS, M. PETRESCU-PRAHOVA, and B. R. CROSS, "Responder communication networks in the world trade center disaster: Implications for modeling of communication within emergency settings," *The Journal of Mathematical Sociology*, vol. 31, no. 2, 2007.
- [6] B. S. Manoj and A. H. Baker, "Communication challenges in emergency response," *Communications of the ACM*, vol. 50, no. 3, pp. 51–53, 2007.
- [7] S. Dawkins, K. Greene, M. Steves, M. Theofanos, Y.-Y. Choong, S. Furman, and S. S. Prettyman, "Public safety communication user needs: Voices of first responders," *Proceedings of the Human Factors and Ergonomics Society Annual Meeting*, vol. 62, no. 1, 2018.
- [8] Y. Huang, W. He, K. Nahrstedt, and W. C. Lee, "Requirements and system architecture design consideration for first responder systems," in *2007 IEEE Conference on Technologies for Homeland Security*, 2007.
- [9] C. Networks. (2020) What is backhaul. <https://www.ceragon.com/what-is-backhaul>.
- [10] Teltonika. (2020) Teltonika rut950 industrial cellular router. <https://teltonika-networks.com/product/rut950/>.
- [11] Cobham. (2020) Cobham explorer 540. <https://www.cobhamsatcom.com/land-mobile-satcom-systems/bgan-m2m/explorer-540/>.
- [12] R. Elements. (2020) Rf elements hg3-tp-s30 horn antenna. <https://www.doubleradius.com/rf-elements-symmetrical-horn-antenna-hg3-tp-s30>.
- [13] Cambium. (2020) Cambium epmp1000. <https://www.cambiumnetworks.com/products/epmp/connectorized-radio/>.
- [14] Honda. (2020) Honda eu10i generator. <https://www.justhonda.co.uk/honda-eu10i-generator.html>.
- [15] PowerOak. (2020) Poweroak ps7 1.000wh solar ac/dc generator. <https://poweroak.eu/en/powerbanks/10054-poweroak-poweroak-ps7-1000wh-solar-ac-dc-generator-8719324080569.html>.
- [16] I. T. Union, "Rec. ITU-R P.1411-6: Propagation data and prediction methods for the planning of short-range outdoor radiocommunication systems and radio local area networks in the frequency range 300 MHz to 100 GHz," Geneva 2012.
- [17] E. Khorov, A. Kiryanov, A. Lyakhov, and G. Bianchi, "A tutorial on ieee 802.11ax high efficiency wlangs," *IEEE Communications Surveys Tutorials*, vol. 21, no. 1, pp. 197–216, 2019.
- [18] D. Deng, K. Chen, and R. Cheng, "IEEE 802.11ax: Next generation wireless local area networks," in *10th International Conference on Heterogeneous Networking for Quality, Reliability, Security and Robustness*, 2014, pp. 77–82.
- [19] B. Bellalta and K. Kosek-Szott, "Ap-initiated multi-user transmissions in ieee 802.11ax wlangs," *Ad Hoc Networks*, vol. 85, pp. 145 – 159, 2019.
- [20] Huawei. (2020) Airengine 8760r-x1e. <https://e.huawei.com/id/products/enterprise-networking/wlan/outdoor-access-points/airengine-8760r-x1-8760r-x1e>.
- [21] Protecli. (2020) FW6C – 6 port intel i5. <https://protectli.com/product/fw6c/>.
- [22] J. Medved, R. Varga, A. Tkacik, and K. Gray, "Opendaylight: Towards a model-driven sdn controller architecture," in *Proceeding of IEEE International Symposium on a World of Wireless, Mobile and Multimedia Networks 2014*, 2014, pp. 1–6.